

Hans Georg K. Gebel

Review of Karin Bartl and Zeidan Kafafi (eds.), 2023. The Neolithic site of eh-Sayyeh, Jordan. Final report on the results from the archaeological investigations 2013-2015. *Orient-Archäologie* 44. Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz. ISBN 978-3-447-12124-8, VIII+335 pages, € 98.

This final publication with co-editor Zeidan Kafafi testifies to Karin Bartl's academically highly commendable disposition to present empirical excavation results swiftly and comprehensively. As is true with her final publication on Shir in the Middle Orontes region (Bartl 2018), a site contemporary with eh-Sayyeh, her pragmatic and timely fulfilment of every excavator's core duty of making excavation results available to the fore. The fact that this was also done within 10 years – without the usual, in the best case, decades-long delay in final excavation publications – explains this editor's devoted academic responsibility that needs to be acknowledged: A review must not only honour this but also take it into account: A final publication geared towards a solid presentation of materials, which aims to make excavation results quickly available, cannot and should not be criticised for not dealing exhaustively with overarching or context-summarising interpretations. Nor should a book review interfere with an excavator's genuine authority and sovereignty to interpret her/ his primary results.¹ Above all, the excavations at eh-Sayyeh had many aspects of a rescue operation, allowing only limited conclusions for some of the materials/ evidence gathered in only nine weeks of excavation during 2013-2015.

Apart from the binding, the volume is solidly produced and attractively furnished (VIII + 335 pages, 283 figures, 72 plates, 18 diagrams, 77 tables, hardback, 21.0 × 29.7 cm), as one would expect from the renowned Harrassowitz-Verlag, Wiesbaden, the new publisher of the *Orient-Archaeology* series of the German Archaeological Institute. The illustrations are reproduced in full colour throughout; separate figure and plate lists name the project and give credits to the authors of the illustrations. The layout is straightforward and user-friendly. The blurring of quite a number of photo illustrations is probably due to digital print settings.

The English-language volume contains five pages of Arabic summaries.

The volume contains ten chapters with a total of 13 subchapters. They focus on the excavation results 2013-2015 represented by contributions from multiple specialists covering key topics deriving from the 1) archaeological contexts (descriptions of the site's geographical and prehistorical context, including the stratigraphy and architectural remains uncovered),

2) material culture (analysis of various artefacts such as pottery, stone tools, and figurines, helping to establish the site's timeline and cultural connections), 3) environmental data (restricted studies on the paleoenvironment and subsistence economy, including botanical and faunal remains), 4) palaeoanthropological findings (investigations into human remains found at the site, shedding light on health, diet, and burial practices of the inhabitants), and 5) chronological frameworks by using 30 radiocarbon dates between the middle Pre-Pottery Neolithic (MPPNB) and the Yarmoukian as well as the relative chronological evidence.

Aspects of the individual chapters are discussed here along with the chapter sequence; the volume's table of contents presented below allows no repeat of the chapter headings.

The foreword to the publication, which is devoted to the acknowledgements, mentions a typical predicament of archaeological field research in Jordan's agricultural areas: the eventual abandonment of archaeological sites to the understandable pressure of landowners to allow their land to be used for agriculture – and the associated incomplete excavations or inaccessibility of important excavation areas of a site.

Chapter I provides basic and concise information. The site (2.5-9.5ha) is located on the terraces of permanent Nahr/ Wadi az-Zarqa where it is joined by Wadi adh-Dhulayl, some 8km NNW of Zarqa city. Conditions for objectives of a planned research excavation were never given in eh-Sayyeh, because the continuous “destruction of the main settlement

areas” between 2013 and 2015 by “levelling for cultivation” prevented this. Despite the tremendous flotation efforts (5000+ litres of soil samples) and over 2000 animal bones identified according to species, it was not sensible to carry out analyses of the palaeo-environmental site setting (*sensu* the reconstruction of the Early Holocene site catchments). The main occupation of the site relates to the FPPNB/ PPNC (7000/ 6900-6400 calBCE). Table I.3 and Map I.8a failed to list Ba`ja and Basta as sites having FPPNB/ PPNC phases/ layers.

The results of the architectural remains are presented in Chapter II comprehensively and exhaustively according to the excavation areas (West, Central, and East Areas) and their “layers”; they take up about a quarter of the volume’s scope. There is no separate chapter on the stratigraphy of the areas, but loci (“unit”) lists accompany the presentation of the 13 squares. The layers are presented in tables and square-wise with descriptions of their structures and other archaeological features; incorporation of the related radiocarbon dates would have been desirable here (for this, Chapter III has to be consulted). The summary on the architecture of eh-Sayyeh does not provide a comparative relative-chronological stratigraphy of the areas with associated radiocarbon dates (included also in Chapter III, providing an absolute-chronological comparison of the excavation areas, *cf.* Table III.4), but concentrates on comparative aspects for the two most significant architectural features of eh-Sayyeh, the Structure 1/ Unit 62 in the West-Area and Structure 1/ Unit 7 in the East Area, combined with a table of radiocarbon dates from Maitland’s Mesa and Wisad Pools. The connection of these two oval structures with the mobile subsistence areas of the 7th millennium’s calBCE eastern steppes is conclusive and necessary: The study of structures and other features in sites of the FPPNB/ PPNC and the PN in the ‘moderate’ zones of Transjordan must become more sensitive to the presence of the ‘steppe signals’ in these sites. There is increasing evidence of findings attesting the presence of the eastern steppe’s mobile inhabitants in the permanent settlements of moderate Transjordan, leaving tangible and intangible footprints of their cultures (*e.g.*, also in the FPPNB/ PPNC of Ba`ja). Already from the beginning of the productive development of the eastern steppes by mobile herders and “industrial” hunting, an intensive exchange between places of the ‘desert and sown’ has to be assumed, most probably also documented at eh-Sayyeh by these two oval structures.

An interesting question about eh-Sayyeh would be the presence of rubble/ gravel layers, which are characteristic of the 7th millennium’s calBCE site stratigraphies (*e.g.*, ‘rubble layers’ attested at `Ain Rahub, Tell Abu Suwwan, Abu Thawwab, `Ain

Ghazal, Wadi Shu`eib, Ghwair, Ba`ja, al-Baseet, Basta, `Ain Jammam, and others).

The eh-Sayyeh radiocarbon database (Chapter III) comprises 30 dates; 27 dates are Neolithic of which one falls into the LPPNB, 21 into the FBBNB/ PPNC and five into the Yarmoukian. The assemblage provides a substantial addition to the Neolithic radiocarbon chronology of the greater Zarqa region, which was already adequately endowed with the databases of `Ain Ghazal, Wadi Shu`eib and Tell Abu Suwwan (*c.* 90 dates). Finally, this chapter provides the assignment of the radiocarbon dates to the individual areas and their layers (“sample-by-sample discussion of the eh-Sayyeh 14C database”) and summarises the settlement phases (p. 113). Chapter III concludes by presenting a palaeoclimatological setting of eh-Sayyeh from a supra-regional perspective (called “palaeoenvironmental setting of eh-Sayyeh” in the publication). This section discusses the continuous settlement sequences of eh-Sayyeh between *c.* 7100 to 6300/ 6250 calBCE against the background of precipitation developments in the late 8th and 7th-millennium calBCE – and identifies the “conspicuous” abandonment of eh-Sayyeh in connection with the “8.2 ka calBP climate event”.

The richly illustrated analysis of the chipped lithic finds (Chapter IV) is the most extensive volume contribution in terms of page numbers (almost 30% of the volume). The description of the lithic finds and their statistical presentation is organised for the upper layers according to 13 important squares and then according to the primary products/ tool classes (!). The 17 flint raw material classes of the 8752 excavated artefacts were recorded descriptively and evaluated statistically per square. The methodological information does not provide insights into the means available for the lithic analysis. Thus, we cannot comment further on the matter that this contribution does not present stratigraphical details related to the core/ debitage and tool classes and treats all assemblages as a single one for all the site’s periods (*cf.* the Conclusions). It is stated that “although a high variability of tools and projectiles is evident, no differences in the transition between the final PPNB/ PPNC and the Pottery Neolithic are observable in eh-Sayyeh. On the contrary, a technological continuity of the flint industry is clearly noticeable” (p. 153). The extensive pictorial documentation of the lithic finds shows arrowheads and several pieces that must have arrived at eh-Sayyeh from the eastern steppes (*e.g.*, Plate IV.27: the upper two; Plate IV.36: the upper left two, the middle left; Plate IV.42: the upper two).

The pottery from eh-Sayyeh (Chapter V) is presented separately according to typology and technology. With a total of 297 excavated sherds, including Chalcolithic, Iron Age and Umayyad, the

information available was very limited. Mostly they represent body sherds; 24 were diagnostic and reported in a catalogue presenting all pieces from the Late Neolithic to the Umayyad periods. The archaeometric examination of 23 sherds from the prehistoric periods revealed a characteristic “low carbonate content, relatively low porosity and the highest initial firing temperature”.

One hundred ‘small finds’ (Chapter VI), mostly fragmented and from the FPPNB/ PPNC, were discovered in the three excavation seasons, comprising a “worktable”, a mortar, three/ four vessel fragments, a flint bowl, two palettes, grinding and handstones, pestles, sling stones, hammerstones, “bangles”, bone tools, mollusc ornaments for the PPNC; a catalogue lists all objects. These rather limited assemblages may relate to the matter that deeper stratigraphies were not reached in many parts of the excavations. The ‘small find’ presentation is supplemented by a functional analysis of selected finds, concentrating on trace wear attested with groundstone and bone items.

The outstanding systematic flotation efforts (5108 litres) of cultural sediments from most of the squares and 132 contexts revealed, despite poor preservation, the domesticated species emmer, lentil, and flax; fig and pistachio must have been foraged. A deciduous oak (*Quercus* cf. *ithaburensis*) and pistachio (*Pistacia* sp.) evidence the site's early Holocene open forest environment.

The faunal remains (Chapter VIII) are predominantly from the FPPNB/ PPNC layers. Using screens with 2mm meshes resulted in a high portion (80%) of unidentifiable bone fragments. Aside from mammals, the nearly 13,000 remains comprise birds, edible helix molluscs, and a freshwater crab. Among the domestic mammals, sheep/ goats (with a dominance of goats?) and cattle dominate; pigs and dogs are present. Among the wild mammals, equids (ass, hemione) and gazelle dominate; foxes, sand cats, and hare are present.

The 25 human bones (Chapter IX) available for the study represent stray finds of three fetuses, one seven-eight and two 9-10 lunar months old individuals, one adolescent and two adults; their presence is interpreted as remains of intra-settlement burials. The proportion of fetuses and Infans II is striking. The analysis of the human remains claims a potential indication for cremation, too.

The closing Chapter X contains the co-editors’ summary and conclusions. It humbly qualifies the findings and finds from eh-Sayyeh as a “contribution to the enlargement of the data from the first half of the 7th millennium”, with “numerous parallels” to the western Mediterranean neighbourhoods in the Southern Levant and evidence for connections to the eastern steppes. The chapter also states that the

findings from eh-Sayyeh leave many aspects of the settlement unclear (e.g., questions of the dual subsistence mode, the potential role and sort of horizontal transhumance).

To summarise, although this publication cannot offer solutions to some key questions of regional diversity in the 7th millennium calBCE, it contributes indispensable primary data for understanding the regional FPPNB/ PPNC and the Yarmoukian. The stratigraphic observations, which were only possible to a limited extent, and the limited excavation areas did not allow for necessary differentiations within the seemingly continuous occupations of eh-Sayyeh between 7150 and 6200 calBCE (radiocarbon dates “rounded to fit into the 100-years-bins”).

The eh-Sayyeh Project, however, stands for another burning and constantly suspended question of research ethics and policy: Can we allow ourselves to continue to carry out mainly research excavations in Jordan (and elsewhere) while largely intact sites resting there for thousands of years are destroyed by modern development in a few years? As cultural anthropologists and heritage preservers, which we should also be as archaeologists, do we not have a duty to support countries like Jordan in the task of carrying out rescue excavations at endangered sites? From the background of this pressing question, the excavators of eh-Sayyeh deserve great appreciation for fulfilling this duty. And that is the real merit behind this publication.

Hans Georg K. Gebel

ex oriente at Berlin Free University
hggebel@zedat.fu-berlin.de

Endnote

¹ This newsletter reviewed the Shir final publication (Rosenstock 2020), which raised the question of how far a book review is permitted to go with checking excavation results.

References

- Bartl K. (ed.)
2018 *The Late Neolithic site of Shir, Syria I. The excavations at the South Area 2006-2009*. Damaszener Forschungen 18. Darmstadt: Wissenschaftliche Buchgesellschaft/ Zabern.
- Rosenstock E.
2020 Review of Karin Bartl (ed.), 2018. The Late Neolithic site of Shir, Syria I. The excavations at the South Area 2006-2009. *Neo-Lithics* 20: A28-31.

(for the volume’s contents, cf. next page)

Volume's Contents

Foreword by Karin Bartl and Zeidan Kafafi

I Introduction by K. Bartl, Z. Kafafi and T. Urban

I.1 The site and its setting

I.2 History of archaeological research in the Wadi az-Zarqa region

I.3 Aims

I.4 Recording methods

II The Architecture

II.1 Introduction by K. Bartl and Z. Kafafi

II.2 The West Area by Z. Kafafi and K. Bartl

II.3 The Central Area by L. Dietrich, K. Pfeiffer and K. Bartl

II.4 The East Area by Z. Kafafi and D. Rokitta-Krumnow

II.5 Summary by K. Bartl and Z. Kafafi

III The Radiocarbon Dates by B. Weninger and K. Bartl

IV The Chipped Lithic Finds by D. Rokitta-Krumnow

V The Pottery

V.1 Pottery Typology by Z. Kafafi

V.2 Pottery Technology by M. al-Naddaf

VI The Small Finds

VI.1 Catalogue of small finds by K. Bartl

VI.2 Functional analyses on selected finds by L. Dietrich

VII The Botanical Remains by R. Neef and K. Bartl

VIII The Faunal Remains by N. Benecke

IX The Human Remains by J. Gresky and K. Bartl

X Summary and Conclusions by K. Bartl and Z. Kafafi

Summary and Conclusions by K. Bartl and Z. Kafafi (in Arabic)

Bibliography

Figures and Plates, Credits

List of Contributors